

FEATURES OF ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF INTRAVENTRICULAR HEMORRHAGE OF THE BRAIN IN CHILDREN

¹Abzalova M.Ya., ²Umarova U.A., ³Bekimbetov K.N.

^{1,2,3}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

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Abstract. *Changes in cerebral blood flow parameters cannot be considered a direct sign of intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH), but they reflect a non-specific response of cerebral hemodynamics to increased intracranial pressure during IVH and characterize the overall severity of brain damage. Doppler ultrasound examination of cerebral blood flow plays an auxiliary role in diagnosing IVH, but undoubtedly has significant prognostic value.*

Keywords: *children, diagnosis, ultrasound examination, hemorrhage, brain.*

Relevance

Intraventricular hemorrhages (IVH) occupy a leading place in the structure of perinatal nervous system damage in newborns and are one of the main causes of fatal outcomes, accounting for 9-27% of cases in full-term infants and up to 70% in premature infants. In 55.4% of cases, previous hemorrhages result in psychoneurological disorders (A.A. Baranov, 2010; O.G. Semenkov, 2012). In Uzbekistan, intraventricular hemorrhages in children constitute approximately 8-15% of newborns (Statistical data on the activities of health institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017).

The primary etiological factor of perinatal pathology of the nervous system, and specifically IVH, is considered to be hypoxia, leading to hemorrhagic damage in newborns. This results in cerebrospinal fluid dynamics disturbances that lead to brain dysfunction. This requires dynamic monitoring by several specialists (J. Volpe, 2012), including ultrasound examination (US) by physicians for timely detection of hydrocephalus development.

To further advance perinatal neurology, there is a need to search for new objective methods for assessing the functional and structural state of the brain. Topical diagnostics can be performed using radiological methods (V.P. Kharchenko, 2011). However, the use of computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is challenging, especially in neonatal intensive care units and in extremely premature infants (T.N. Trofimova, 2009), as well as for continuous dynamic monitoring of cerebrospinal fluid dynamics and hemodynamics. All of the above makes this an urgent issue that requires further study.

Objective of the Study. The aim of the study was to optimize the diagnosis of intraventricular hemorrhages (IVH) in children through the use of modern ultrasound methods.

Materials and Methods. The basis of this work was the results of neurosonographic examinations of 90 children with IVH. All patients underwent brain ultrasound using standard and polypositional neurosonography (stNSG and pNSG). All children in the hospital population were at an increased risk for developing IVH. The ratio of newborns to children aged 1–12 months was approximately the same (52.5% and 47.5%), with a significantly higher proportion of boys (71.2%). More than half of the children (61.8%) were born through natural delivery in the head-first presentation. Almost a quarter of the patients (22.2%) were delivered via cesarean section.

Complicated delivery situations were also common: rapid labor occurred in 4.0% of cases, secondary uterine inertia in 4.0%, vacuum extraction in 6.0%, and breech or footling presentations in 3.0% of cases. Obstetric trauma, as an etiological factor for IVH development, was diagnosed in 17.8% of cases with clinical manifestations (pain syndrome, general brain and focal neurological symptoms) and signs of mechanical skull injury (cephalohematoma, pathological head shape, skull fractures, osteodiastasis of the occipital bone). Obstetric traumatic injuries were diagnosed in 12.9% of children without neurological symptoms, with IVH grade I. Hypoxic-ischemic damage to the central nervous system was identified in 3% of children with grade III-IV IVH, and hypoxic-traumatic damage was seen in 4%. Postnatal traumatic brain injury was the cause of IVH in 25.7% of children. Domestic cranial injuries occurred in 20.8% of cases, usually following accidental falls from the hands of adults, changing tables, or beds. Traumatic brain injuries caused by road traffic accidents were recorded in 1% of cases. In one child, multiple skull fractures were found, accompanied by massive IVH, a brain contusion focus, and severe parenchymal damage in the form of subcortical necrosis; in three other children, subacute bilateral IVH was identified, along with post-traumatic cystic changes. Comprehensive clinical, laboratory, and instrumental examinations included detailed medical history collection, physical examination, and neurosonographic examination at the Republican Perinatal Center and the Republican Scientific Center for Neurosurgery using ultrasound diagnostic equipment such as Sonoscape 5000, Aplio 500 ("Toshiba," Japan), and Mirror 2. The control group consisted of 20 healthy children of the same age. In the control group, we studied practically healthy children. High-frequency sectoral probes with frequencies of 5.0 and/or 7.5 MHz were used for the ultrasound examination of the brain in newborns and young children. Convex probes were used when lateral brain structures were limited in view. The severity of the condition did not contraindicate neurosonography. The scanning was carried out in B-mode, color Doppler mode (CDK), and pulsed Doppler imaging. All children underwent NSG within the first 1-2 days of admission to the hospital, without the need for additional preparation for the study. Polypositional NSG (pNSG) was performed with the child lying on their back, followed by turning the head to the right and left. Patients in critical condition on artificial ventilation were examined in the presence of a resuscitation specialist.

Methodology

The methodology included polypositional scanning using both traditional access through the large fontanel and access through the occipital, mastoid fontanel, temporal access, sutures, and through bone defects in cases of skull fractures. Scanning was performed in frontal, sagittal, axial, and oblique planes using convex and high-frequency linear probes. In addition to the grayscale mode, Doppler techniques were used. Color Doppler (CDK) was applied to assess the vascularization of the meningeal spaces and brain, while the pulsed Doppler mode allowed for quantitative measures of cerebral blood flow and the identification of cerebral hemodynamic disorders.

The protocol for polypositional neurosonography (pNSG) included the following points:

- Differentiation and symmetry of brain structures
- Presence or absence of displacement of midline brain structures
- Assessment of brain parenchyma (echogenicity, presence of diffuse and focal changes, the pattern of sulci and gyri)
- Size of internal ventricular spaces: lateral ventricles, III and IV ventricles

Assessment of the vascular plexuses, ependyma of the ventricles, presence of inclusions in the cerebrospinal fluid

Size of external ventricular spaces (width of the subarachnoid space on the convex surface of the cerebral hemispheres, width of the interhemispheric fissure)

Presence or absence of pathological meningeal collections (location, shape, size, echogenicity, and structure)

Patency of cerebrospinal fluid pathways

Assessment of structures in the posterior cranial fossa: symmetry of cerebellar hemispheres, size of the large occipital cistern, presence of paracerebellar meningeal collections, their size and structure, and the presence of echogenic inclusions in the transverse venous sinuses

Doppler parameters of cerebral blood flow: maximum systolic blood flow velocity (V_{max}) in the anterior cerebral artery; minimum diastolic blood flow velocity (V_{min}) in the anterior cerebral artery; resistance index (RI) in the anterior cerebral artery; blood flow velocity in the Galen vein and transverse sinuses

Research Results. When analyzing the clinical course of IVH, we observed a correlation between the severity of neurological symptoms and the degree of hemorrhage. In 5 children with grade I of IVH and 15 children in the control group, neurological manifestations were not significantly different. The onset of neurological symptoms varied from 1–2 to 8–9 days of life. In 5 children with grade I IVH, a moderately expressed central nervous system (CNS) depression syndrome was observed, characterized by the suppression of unconditioned reflexes, 4 children had reduced spontaneous motor activity, 6 children exhibited decreased muscle tone, and 2 children had tendon reflexes with accompanying oculomotor disorders. By the 2nd–3rd week of life, all children became more active, with signs of hyperexcitability syndrome emerging — increased spontaneous motor activity, reactivation of unconditioned reflexes, muscle dystonia, and hyperreflexia. Two children with grade I of IVH experienced seizure syndrome in the neonatal period.

In 15 children with grade II of IVH, the CNS depression syndrome was more pronounced. Disorders of consciousness, sopor, and, in more severe cases, coma were observed. In 4 children, pupillary reflex abnormalities were noted, and in 7 children, oculomotor disorders were often associated with bulbar disturbances (such as impaired sucking, swallowing, breathing, and cardiac abnormalities). Differences with the control group were statistically significant only in terms of the frequency of seizure development (5 children).

Grade III of IVH had the most severe course. These children remained in a comatose state for a long time, with respiratory disturbances requiring mechanical ventilation.

Research Results (continued)

In many cases, high-grade IVH was accompanied by bleeding into the III and IV ventricles. The III ventricle was optimally visualized during scanning through the squama of the temporal bone, and during the acute phase of the condition, blood within it appeared as highly echogenic content. Over time, the clot transformed similarly to the thrombi in the lateral ventricles: its central part became hypo-anechoic, and the contour appeared sharply echodense.

A severe complication of high-grade IVH was bleeding into the posterior cranial fossa. It was difficult to visualize during neurosonography, so non-standard scanning approaches were used. The most common finding was bleeding into the large cistern. Fresh blood appeared as echogenic content uniformly filling the entire cistern. Its size typically did not increase during the

acute phase of the disease. Frequently, high-grade IVH led to a blockage of cerebrospinal fluid pathways, with a rapid increase in the dilation of the cerebrospinal fluid pathways. Fragments of thrombi were sometimes identified within their lumen. The blockage of cerebrospinal fluid pathways sometimes occurred due to an adhesive process or the addition of inflammatory changes. The most commonly affected areas were the narrowest points: the Sylvian aqueduct and the Monro foramina. Blockage at the level of the Monro foramina caused significant dilation of the lateral ventricles on the blocked side. Blockage at the level of the Sylvian aqueduct led to rapid enlargement of both the lateral and III ventricles.

Blockage in the large cistern was also observed, accompanied by significant and sharp deterioration in the child's condition, affecting vital functions. In this case, cerebrospinal fluid pathways were dilated throughout their course, and the large cistern took on a spherical shape, pushing the medulla oblongata ventrally.

Grade III of IVH was easily diagnosed using neurosonography, with the characteristic sign being the parenchymal component — not only the thrombus in the lumen of the lateral ventricle but also a hemorrhagic focus in the brain parenchyma, directly adjacent to the thrombus in the ventricle. Over time, ventriculomegaly developed, and the hemorrhage in the brain parenchyma led to the formation of a large porencephalic cyst. The parenchymal component of grade III of IVH could occur in any part of the brain adjacent to the lateral ventricle, and in all cases, the contour of the lateral ventricle was not visualized. In massive hemorrhages, the displacement of midline brain structures was observed, with a shift to the opposite side of the hemorrhage, severely disrupting brain anatomy.

In addition to B-mode scanning, all patients with sonographic signs of IVH underwent Doppler evaluation of cerebral hemodynamics.

The description provided outlines the use of color Doppler imaging (CDI) and pulse wave Doppler (PWD) to assess cerebral hemodynamics in newborns, particularly those with intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH). Here's an English translation and summary of the symptoms identified:

1. Flickering Vessel Pattern Symptom: This symptom was detected using CDI when there was a marked decrease in arterial blood flow velocity during diastole and a significant increase in vascular resistance. The color change of the arterial blood flow from red to blue indicated the presence of reversed flow during diastole, which corresponds to a resistance index (RI) greater than 1.0. This symptom was identified in 9.8% of children with ultrasound (US) signs of IVH. In all cases, the condition was considered very severe, and all the children were treated in the intensive care unit (ICU).

2. Increased Resistance Characteristics of Cerebral Arterial Blood Flow: This symptom is a quantitative equivalent of the flickering vessel pattern. Due to the urgent nature of the situation and the generalized cerebral hemodynamic response to IVH in infants, measurements of blood flow characteristics were taken in the anterior cerebral artery (ACA) and, less frequently, the pericallosal artery. Increased resistance characteristics were identified when the RI in the ACA was greater than 0.7. This symptom was present in 39.0% of children with US signs of IVH. In the acute phase of massive IVH and periventricular hemorrhage (PVH), there was a sharp increase in the RI in the ACA to 1.0 or higher, observed in 9.8% of cases. In 3.6% of cases, amplitude modulation of the arterial blood flow was noted depending on the act of breathing, indicating a

possible autoregulatory dysfunction in cerebral blood flow. There were no cases where a decrease in RI was observed in the acute phase.

3. Change in Blood Flow Velocity in the ACA: Among the patients with US signs of IVH, the maximum arterial blood flow velocity (V_{max}) was within reference values in 53.7% of the children, elevated to 0.9-1.2 m/s in 12.2%, and decreased in 7.3%. Patients with normal speed values in the ACA had varying RI values: 31.7% had normal RI, 6.1% had increased RI values less than 1.0, and 6.1% had values greater than 1.0. An increase in V_{max} in the ACA with increased RI was observed in 13.4% of patients, and only in 1.2% of patients with normal peripheral resistance. A decrease in V_{max} was observed in 1.2% of patients with normal RI and in 1.2% of patients with sharply increased RI.

These findings emphasize the importance of monitoring cerebral hemodynamics using Doppler imaging techniques in newborns with IVH to assess the severity of the condition and guide appropriate clinical interventions.

The symptom of pulsatile venous blood flow in the Galen vein was observed in 2.4% of patients with ultrasound (US) signs of intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH). All the children had massive IVH and were in a critical condition in the intensive care unit (ICU). In all cases, there were significant accompanying central hemodynamic disturbances, making it difficult to definitively conclude that changes in the Galen vein blood flow were solely a consequence of the IVH itself. Cerebral arterial blood flow disturbances in these patients were significant but not critical.

Conclusion:

Thus, PNSG (pulsed color Doppler sonography) allowed for diagnosing IVH not only in B-mode but also by using Doppler techniques to assess blood flow. Summarizing the study on the echographic signs of IVH in newborns and infants under 3 months old, it can be concluded that STNSG (standard sonography) performed at the beginning of each infant's examination does not always reveal the primary echographic signs of IVH or accurately diagnose the pathology. STNSG is only capable of visualizing large IVHs and identifying indirect signs, while PNSG can visualize both large IVHs that are missed on STNSG and small IVHs.

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